

An Elegant and Concise Proof of the Infinitude of Primes

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Abstract

In this paper, we present an elegant and concise proof of the infinitude of prime numbers based on the fundamental properties of prime numbers.

Theorem. There are infinitely many prime numbers.

Proof. Let \mathbb{P} be finite and $N = \frac{1}{2} \prod_{p \in \mathbb{P}} p$. Since $\gcd(N - 1, N) = 1$, so $N - 1 = 2^k$ for some integer k and $7|2^k + 1$, which is impossible. \square